

INTERNAL FRICTION IN ALUMINUM-BORON FIBRES COMPOSITE MATERIAL

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ABSTRACT

To study the relaxation mechanisms of the internal stresses in the composite material aluminium - boron, the method of internal friction has been used in the present work. The contribution of the interfaces into the process of general damping inside the composite has been determined. It has been shown that the interface damping is mainly conditioned by the matrix creeping occurring in the near boundary region as a result of the interface gliding. The temperature dependence of the internal stresses occurring in the matrix of the composite Al-B during heating within 600 to 750 K has been obtained.

INTRODUCTION

In the process of mechanical loading or temperature treatment the composite materials (CM) accumulate irreversible strains as a result of redistribution of internal stresses which in its turn is a result of activities of different mechanisms. In the case when a CM consists of high modulus fibres and the matrixes of higher plasticity, the mechanisms of stress redistribution are the matrix creeping and slippage of fibres along the interfaces [1]. The sequence of action of each of the participating mechanisms of damage accumulation depends on many factors, in particular, on the CM composition, technology of its production, treatment temperature, loading conditions, etc. The initial stages of defect formation in the CM both in the case of the longitudinal mechanical loading and in the case temperature treatment have many in common, so one should consider one type of loading, for example, the formation of the stressed state by thermocycling. In the case of such type of loading, damages are accumulated as a result of internal stresses of a thermal origin which occur because of the difference in coefficients of thermal expansion of phases forming a composite. This problem has been considered in [2-4], which deal with the determination of internal stresses in the CM matrix using a mechanical model which assumed the viscous-elastic behaviour of the composite under strain. The analytical model for the CM proposed in the work of Garmong [2] assumes an ideal bond at the interfaces. So, according to the proposed model, damage accumulation in the composite seems to occur only due to the matrix creeping. The real situation turns out to be more complicated. The conclusions reported in [3, 4] evidence about the fundamental contribution of interfaces into damage accumulation in the CM. In

spite of the evident actuality, many aspects of this problem of defect formation and absorption of the elastic energy in the composite materials remained obscured because its experimental investigation is complicated. To investigate the nature of internal stresses relaxation in the CM aluminium-boron, the presented paper applies the method of internal friction (IF) [5] which is based on the new approach with analysis of obtained experimental results. This approach consists in accounting the additive contribution of each component as well as interfaces into the resulting damping of CM.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE AND MATERIALS

The test substance was Al-B composite prepared by hot compaction. Separate components of the composite were also examined: highly-deformed aluminium and boron fibers 100 μm in diameter. The boron fiber content by volume was 45%. The internal friction of the composite and its components was studied in the 10^{-4} Pa vacuum over the temperature range from 300 to 900 K using a torsion pendulum, with the sample deformation amplitudes being 10^{-6} . The heating rate was 5 K/min. The composite and aluminium samples measured $1 \times 1 \times 100 \text{ mm}^3$ and the boron fiber length 20 mm. The experiments were performed at the torsional vibration frequency of 1 Hz.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As it is known [6], the longitudinal modulus of the normal elasticity of the CM can be well approximated using the "mixture rule". By the analogy, as well as basing on physical considerations, the internal friction of the CM containing the N of phases can be described by equation

$$Q^{-1} = \sum_{i=1}^N Q_i^{-1} V_i + Q_b^{-1} \quad (1)$$

where the Q_i^{-1} and V_i are the internal friction and the volume fraction of the i -th phase; the Q_b^{-1} is the internal friction conditioned by the interfaces ("boundary damping"). In the case of the two-phase CM, as it is the case with the investigated material, equation (1), without taking into account the contribution of the interfaces has the form

$$Q_{\text{th}}^{-1} = Q_m^{-1} V_m + Q_f^{-1} V_f \quad (2)$$

where the indexes "m" and "f" refer to the matrix and fibre, respectively.

Figure 1 demonstrates the temperature dependences the IF for the composite aluminium-boron and separately for its components - aluminium and boron fibre, obtained in the process of heating with the rate of 5 K/min (curves 1-3). Curve 4 demonstrates the theoretical dependence $Q^{-1}(T)$ for the CM Al-B which has been obtained using equation (2). One can see satisfactory coincidence of experimental

and theoretical dependences $Q^{-1}(T)$ up to 600 K. At higher temperatures when diffusion processes start their development at the interfaces, the difference between experimental and theoretical values of damping becomes essential.

Figure 1. The temperature dependence of the internal friction for: aluminium - 1; boron fibre - 2; composite material Al-B - 3 and for the model sample CM Al-B, plotted using equation (2) - 4. The frequency is 1 Hz.

To analyse the processes conditioned by the existence of the interfaces in the CM, which occur at higher temperatures and taking into account the expressions (1) and (2), the contribution of the "boundary damping" into the general IF of the composite was determined

$$Q_b^{-1} = Q^{-1} - (Q_m^{-1} V_m + Q_f^{-1} V_f) \quad (3)$$

Figure 2 demonstrates the dependence $Q_b^{-1}(T)$ obtained for the CM Al-B using the expression (3) and the results presented in Fig.1. It is seen, that when temperature increased from 300 to 600 K the "boundary damping" within the limits of error is at a zero level, consequently, the intensity of relaxation processes conditioned by the internal stresses is low, the mechanical slippage at the interfaces is absent, i.e. the bond of fibres with matrix exists at the molecular level. At higher temperatures diffusion processes due to the instability of the CM [7] start their development in the aluminium-boron, so the effects, which appear in the $Q_b^{-1}(T)$ dependence at temperatures higher than 600 K can be interpreted in a definite way.

So, the small peak of the "boundary damping" at 630 K seems to be related to the interdiffusion processes which determine the growth of the intermetalloid phase AlB_2 . The correlation of the effective diffusion coefficient value ($D=4 \cdot 10^{-21} \text{ m}^2/\text{c}$) which was evaluated using the peak temperature position [5] with the results of the work [8] when interpolated in the region of the peak temperature, evidence in this favours.

Figure 2. The temperature dependence of the interface damping in the CM Al-B.

The growth of the Q_b^{-1} with temperatures higher than 600 K seems to be conditioned by elementary processes of the interface gliding. Indeed, the increase of internal stresses in the CM with temperature elevation results in the loss of stability of its mechanical state. Since the interfaces are the most weak element of the real composites with a metallic matrix [7], one should first of all expect damaging in the state of this element. Macroscopic evidence of this damaging is an interface gliding which seems to be the consequence of elementary processes of the internal stress relaxation in the CM phases at the near boundary region, mainly in the matrixes of higher plasticity. These processes are the base the mechanism of the matrix creeping at high temperatures. Taking into account the similiarity of the dependence $Q_b^{-1}(T)$ at temperatures higlier than 600 K and that for materials which were in the process of creeping [9], and all the above mentioned, the following interpretation of the temperature dependence of the "boundary damping" was proposed.

The dependence of the IF of the material under creeping on the strain rate of $\dot{\epsilon}$ can be described by equation [10]

$$Q^{-1} = \frac{E \Omega}{\omega k T} \dot{\epsilon} \quad (4)$$

where the E is the Young's modulus, the Ω is the activation volume, the ω is the frequency of sample oscillations, k is the Boltzman constant. In this case $\dot{\epsilon}$ means the rate of the CM matrix creeping, it is mainly determined by the gliding along the interfaces which is the slower process.

Using equation (4), the known dependence $Q_b^{-1}(T)$ and the characteristic values $E=5.7 \cdot 10^{10}$ to $4.3 \cdot 10^{10}$ Pa (within the internal 600 to 900 K), $\Omega=10^{-28}$ m³ [11], the

dependence of the matrix strain rate in the CM Al-B on heating temperature (Fig.3) was obtained. The reasonable values of $\dot{\epsilon}$ which correlate with the results of the other works [12], confirm the assumed nature of the "boundary damping".

Figure 3. The temperature dependence of the creeping rate of the CM Al-B matrix during heating.

Temperature dependence of strain the rate in material found in the case of high-temperature creeping is usually described by equation [12]

$$\dot{\epsilon} = (\epsilon_0 / T) \exp [- Q(\sigma) / kT] \quad (5)$$

where the ϵ_0 is the predexponential factor, the $Q(\sigma)$ is the activation energy of creeping depending on the internal stresses σ . Expression (5) was used to understand the nature of the processes controlling the creeping of the aluminium matrix in the CM Al-B during heating. Figure 4 demonstrated the temperature dependence of the matrix strain rate in the aluminium-boron composite, plotted in the coordinates $\ln(\dot{\epsilon} \cdot T) - T^{-1}$, which allowed the creeping activation energy to be determined. The presented dependence within the interval 700 to 900 K falls well on a straight line, the slope of which corresponds to the activation energy 0.4 eV. In the temperature region 600 K to 750 K the slope of the dependence presented in Fig. 4 is constantly changing.

One should note that the activation energy of the processes which are responsible for relaxation of the internal stresses in the CM Al-B in the temperature region 450 K has been reported in the work [3] and its value turns out to be equal to 0.4 eV. In this connection one should assume that in the real CM Al-B when temperature is changing, the main mechanism of the internal stress relaxation is the slippage along the interfaces which is controlled by the processes with the activation energy of 0.4 eV. The deviation of the dependence demonstrated in Fig.4 out of the straight line, corresponding the given value of the activation energy relates to the growth of compressing stresses in the composite matrix. In the temperature region near 450 K

Figure 4. The temperature dependence of the creeping rate of the CM Al-B matrix plotted to determine the activation energy.

and above 750 K the internal stresses in the matrix of the CM Al-B are low, so the obtained effective value of the activation energy is close to the real one.

The presented speculations allow the determination of the internal stress in the CM Al-B matrix in the temperature interval 600 to 750 K during heating. For this purpose let us use the relation [5]

$$Q = Q_0 - \sigma\Omega \quad (6)$$

Here the Q is the activation energy of the process in a crystal which is under effect of stresses σ , the Q_0 is the activation energy without stresses. Figure 5 demonstrates the dependence of internal stresses in the composite matrix in the near boundary region which was plotted using the expression (6) and experimental results of Fig. 4 dealing with the dependence of the activation energy upon temperature. The obtained dependence $\sigma(T)$ demonstrated in Fig. 5 agrees qualitatively with the similar dependence which has been obtained analytically in [2]. The maximum value of matrix internal stresses at 650 K which is equal to 23.8 MPa, according to the model proposed in [2], can be interpreted as the limit of material fluidity under given temperature. When temperature rises above this limit, the stress in the matrix starts falling due to the creepage and interface gliding.

The obtained value of the activation energy (0.4 eV) is close to the value of the vacancy migration energy in aluminium. A decrease of this value in real case seems to be a result of strains in the near boundary layer due to high defect concentration in it and lattice deformation. As a result of heating the dilatation and shear stresses grow near the interfaces which leads to increased vacancy concentration. Being affected by shear stresses, the interfaces appear to be in the non-equilibrium state which results in the sink of vacancies towards them and initiation of elementary acts of slippage.

Figure 5. The temperature dependence of the internal stresses in the CM Al-B matrix during heating.

Figure 6. The temperature dependence of the internal friction for the composite material Al-B in the case of heating - 1 and cooling - 2. The frequency is 1 Hz.

In the case of cooling from higher temperatures which are close to the temperatures of the composite Al-B production, the internal stresses increase very fast [2], so the mechanism of diffusion slippage plays a significant role for accumulation of damages only at initial stage of cooling. With further cooling the internal stresses have no time to relax in terms of the above mentioned mechanism and the delicate bonds between the matrix and the fibre start their destruction. As a result, the internal friction of the CM in the case of cooling within the range of 300 to 500 K turns out to be higher than in the case of heating (Fig. 6). In such a way the dependence of

the CM internal friction on temperature shows a characteristic hysteresis in the process of a thermocycle the loop value of which may serve a quantitative characteristic for the produced in CM damages.

CONCLUSIONS

In such a way, in the presented paper we proposed the method for determining the temperature dependence of the internal stresses and mechanisms of their relaxation on the base of the new approach in the course of investigations of the internal friction of composite materials. It has been shown that the relaxation of internal stresses in the matrix of the CM Al-B occurs due to the interface gliding which is controlled by the processes with 0.4 eV activation energy. The diffusion migration of vacancies in the near boundary region seems to rank among such processes. A temperature dependence of internal stresses in the matrix of the CM Al-B was determined in the process of heating in the interval 600 to 750 K. The limit of fluidity of the aluminium matrix at 650 K (23.8 MPa) was determined as the maximum value of the internal stresses found at their temperature dependence. The temperature dependence of the internal friction for the Al-B composite shows the hysteresis in the process of the thermocycle 300-900-300 K which is the quantitative characteristic of the occurring in material damages.

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